

NAVIGATIONAL NEEDS FOR CURRENT AND FUTURE HIGH-G
INERTIAL MEASUREMENT UNITS

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ABSTRACT

A large number of commercial and military applications call for the use of inertial measurement units (IMUs). These applications vary vastly, however a new era is dawning where the need for and utilization of IMUs which can navigate through steady-state high accelerations are growing. These instruments will have to be very near or completely solid state because of the high acceleration loading. The performance of these instruments will be characterized by broader dynamic range, minimal nonlinear effects, and higher noise rejection capability. These instruments must also exhibit small volume, low power, and low cost. An example of this type of IMU is the one needed for the Advanced Kinetic Energy Missile (ADKEM).

NOMENCLATURE

ADKEM = Advanced Kinetic Energy Missile
CEP = Circular Error Probable
g = acceleration unit (1g=9.8m/sec)
HMMWV = Highly Mobile Multi-Wheeled Vehicle
IMU = Inertial Measurement Unit
LH = Light Helicopter
mrad = Milliradian
mg = Milli-g
PPM = Parts Per Million
SAM = Surface-to-Air-Missile
μrad = micro-radian

INTRODUCTION

The ability of any self-guided airborne system to execute its mission is directly related to the performance of its inertial instruments and its initial instrument alignment. Historically, the tactical missile arena has utilized the medium to low accuracy inertial systems for two major reasons. One, the overall system performance could be accomplished

without the higher accuracy inertial grade systems. Secondly, and most importantly, the cost of an inertial grade system was prohibitive for large volume tactical missile production. However, with the ever-advancing performance of the state-of-the-art weapons platforms (i.e. aircraft, helicopters, armored vehicles, etc.) the performance requirements placed on the tactical missile systems which engage them begin to approach the higher accuracy more costly inertial grade devices. One element of the increased performance requirements is the higher acceleration environment. The instruments that appear in this arena take on two forms: the very high acceleration environment of a cannon launched system where the inertial instruments are non-operational until they returned to a low-g regime and the extremely expensive strategic systems which operate in a moderate acceleration environment. The void which currently exists for the tactical missile systems is the capability to navigate through a sustained high acceleration environment. Developments in other technologies associated with tactical missiles such as higher specific impulse motors, lighter, stronger composite materials for motor casings and missile skins, higher bandwidth, more compact actuators for continuous control, and faster, more powerful computers all provide the conditions to develop an unprecedented high performance high-g tactical missile. The Advanced Kinetic Energy Missile (ADKEM) demonstration program is utilizing recent inertial instrument developments in the high-g non-operating arena and developing the capability to navigate in the high-g environment.

This paper uses the ADKEM IMU performance requirements as a platform to discuss various error sources and their contribution to the ADKEM system performance and also to indicate possible applications of this technology for the future.

ADKEM MISSION

The ADKEM system is designed to be a multi-role tactical missile able to engage high speed fixed wing aircraft, helicopters, and armored targets. The objective as the name implies is to use the missile's kinetic energy to defeat the target of choice. The ADKEM design is projected to have more than twice the penetration capability and 5 to 6 times the amount of total delivered energy than current armament. Additional benefits are gained from the ability to fire from full defilade and providing immediate 360 degrees of fire capability, eliminating turret or rack swivel time.

The ADKEM engagement scenario, as pictured in figure 1, has a design capability of attacking heavy armor at ranges of 300 meters to 5 kilometers and aircraft at ranges of 1 kilometer to 10 kilometers. ADKEM is not limited to a particular launch platform either. It is launchable from such platforms as the Bradley, HMMWV, or LH. For the analysis and discussions presented here it is assumed that ADKEM is launched from an armored system in defilade.

The ADKEM missile system consists of a long slender centerbody (approximately 2 inches in diameter) with four boost motors attached around the circumference, see figure 2. The system has three phases of flight; the orientation phase, the boost phase, and the coast phase. The orientation phase occurs during and after vertical launch. During launch the missile is lofted vertically for approximately 50 feet and utilizes an "orientation package" which is powered by a gas generator to provide the energy to achieve line-of-sight to the target or the capture basket of the millimeter wave radar. The boost phase follows and is the stage wherein the missile accelerates under inertial guidance to either a close-in target or the capture window for the millimeter wave radar. At this point the motors are explosively released and the missile coast to the target under command-to-line-of-sight guidance by the millimeter wave radar.

ADKEM ENGAGEMENT SEQUENCE

Figure 1. ADKEM ENGAGEMENT SEQUENCE

ADKEM
Advance Kinetic Energy Missile

Figure 2. ADKEM SYSTEM LAYOUT

ADKEM is roll stabilized with aft actuators for continuous control authority instead of lateral impulse thrusters. The actuators serve as the body control device in all three phases of the flight (i.e. orientation, boost, and coast) but in very different ways. After expulsion from the launch canister the fins actuate the thrust control valves of the orientation package directly. The system executes a series of orienting maneuvers, while translating vertically. The orientation package is used in order to achieve the pointing accuracy needed. During this phase the system can see roll rates as high as 1500 °/sec and pitch rates up to 500 °/sec. Once the missile is pointing at the target within ±5° and the missile is well clear of the millimeter wave antenna, the boost motors are ignited. The exhaust of the boost motors discards the orientation package and impacts upon the fins giving them thrust divert capability. The four boost motors generate approximately 50,000 lbs of force on the 100+ lb missile yielding an initial acceleration loading of 500-gs. The .35 second burn culminates in a final acceleration environment of 1000-gs and speeds at or above 2000 meters per second. At the end of the burn the motors are released and the centerbody coasts (at Mach 6) to the target. The release of the motors reduces the drag of the system and allows

it to extend its range of effectiveness. During the coast phase the actuators have more than ample dynamic pressure to provide the necessary control forces to guide the system to the target. During both the boost phase and the coast phase the actuators have the capability to generate 125-gs of lateral acceleration.

ADKEM IMU

One of the challenging opportunities on the ADKEM demonstration program is the navigation of the system through the high-g boost environment. The inertial instruments involved must not only navigate through the launch environment and provide pointing accuracies of ±5 degrees during the orientation phase. They must also be able to navigate through the 1000-g boost environment and provide a ½ meter CEP at 500 meters. The ½ meter CEP at 500 meters requirement is drawn from the short range anti-armor engagement scenario. The performance characteristics necessary to accomplish this are discussed on the next section.

The centerbody space allocation for the IMU is 8 inches in length for the demonstration program and 4 inches for the tactical version. The diameter is 1.79 inches, however this is somewhat misleading since there is a flat .3 inches up from the bottom to allow for cabling to pass through the section (see figure 3 IMU Cross Section). The volume described here must house the gyros,

Figure 3. IMU CROSS SECTION

accelerometers, and all associated electronics. The IMU must provide delta- Θ and delta-V updates at 500 hertz with a minimum of 12 bits of accuracy. The bandwidth of the sensors must be at or greater than 150 Hertz to accommodate the autopilot response time and phase and gain margins.

ADKEM IMU ERROR BUDGET

As presented earlier, the driving case for the inertial instruments error budget is that of a heavy armored target at the longest range it must navigate and just prior to being captured by the millimeter wave beam. For longer ranges the beam rider guidance takes over and relieves the IMU of its navigation responsibilities. To achieve target defeat at 500 meters the missile must navigate to within a 1 meter circle with high reliability. One would certainly not like to miss a heavy armored target at close range. To accommodate this requirement a 95% probability function was used with the 1 meter diameter to generate the CEP value of approximately $\frac{1}{2}$ meter. With this CEP, a back-of-the-envelope set of calculations were generated to establish preliminary performance characteristics while the 6 Degree-Of-Freedom simulation was being brought on line. The preliminary calculations are outlined in Table 1(1).

The results of the back-of-the-envelope calculations were substantiated by the 6-Degree-of-Freedom monte carlo simulation. The high fidelity non-linear simulation yielded a CEP of 0.66 meters using the final inertial instrument error budget (2).

The chief lessons learned from the generation of the error budget for ADKEM was that the typical errors which dictate system performance were not the major driving force here. The gyro scale factor stability requirement is not too surprising but the accelerometer dynamic range, scale factor stability, and especially the cross-axis g-sensitivity projected the need for devices which are currently not available. A survey of the gyro market produced some options in both performance and technology for the demonstration program. The gyro technologies that have potential application in this arena are: coriolis sensors and optical sensors.

The coriolis sensors have several embodiments but those which have shown the most promise thus far are the tuning fork technologies (e.g. quartz, steel, ceramic). Size, weight, and power are among its chief attributes. The performance of the current devices is marginal for the tactical IMU.

Table 1. ADKEM Initial Error Budget

ERROR SOURCE	INITIAL VALUE	NAV. ERROR (M)	FINAL VALUE	NAV. ERROR (M)
GYRO				
Bias Drift	200°/hr	0.0428	30°/hr	0.006
Scale Factor Stab.	1000ppm	0.785	100ppm	0.078
G-Sens Drift	.02°/sec/g	0.15	0.3°/hr/g	.00063
Misalignment	200μrad	0.1	20μrad	.01
ACCELEROMETER				
Bias Drift	100mg	0.89	1.0mg	.0089
Scale Factor Stab.	1000ppm	0.50	300ppm	0.0037
Misalignment	200μrad	0.1	200μrad	0.1
IA Anioelastic Effects	40μg/g ²	0.183	40μg/g ²	0.183
Cross-Axis G-Sens.	10.0μg/g ²	4.41	1.0μg/g ²	0.441
Initial Align.	1.0 mrad	0.5	0.5mrad	0.25
TOTALS (RSS)		4.63		0.54

The optical sensors (e.g. Ring Laser Gyros, Interferometric Fiber Optic Gyros, and Resonant Fiber Optic Gyros) have recently demonstrated significant size and weight reductions while maintaining good performance. Thus, the rate sensing capability for a high-g IMU is available. These technologies are still primarily in the corporate IR&D and prototype stage but they are available.

The accelerometer which can resolve 1 milli-g in a 1000-g environment while providing cross-axis acceleration rejection of 1 micro-g/g² has not been identified. The technologies that are available are the force-rebalance accelerometers and the open-loop resonating beam accelerometers. The force-rebalance accelerometers have several problems to overcome to be fully functional in the high-g environment: namely, size, power, and price. The current precision accelerometers which have some of the necessary performance characteristics would have to increase their torque strength dramatically while at the same time reducing their size considerably. The inherently labor-intensive construction techniques used to manufacture the accelerometer are not conducive to an inexpensive instrument used in a high production tactical missile program. The alternate technology, monolithic chemically etched

resonating beam accelerometers, on the other hand has several inherent benefits. They are fundamentally digital output devices; which allow for simpler more robust electronics. They utilize monolithic fabrication techniques; which lends itself to a significant cost reduction for manufacturing. Recent performance demonstrations of devices in this technology indicate the capability of meeting and potentially exceeding the goals identified in the error budget. The monolithic construction also greatly reduces concerns over weight, size, and power. So even though there is no device currently available to do the ADKEM mission, there is a viable means to obtain one.

FUTURE FOR HIGH-G IMUS

The ADKEM demonstration program is a developmental system which is manipulating currently available technologies into a form which can revolutionize the tactical engagement environment. A key component in the development and demonstration is the Inertial Measurement Unit. The IMU spawned from this effort will open a new era from which system designers in the military and the commercial world will be able to strive toward and achieve loftier goals. An IMU which can navigate through

a 1000-g environment can be used in a multitude of defense postures. Examples of these uses are self-protection systems for tanks, ships, radar installations (both mobile and fixed), SAM sites, bunkers, and aircraft; precision guided munitions; high-g submunitions; precision navigation for high altitude interception; and others. A device of this nature could also provide a diverse utilization to the commercial community. Examples of this diversity are: precision automated mining equipment, navigation of drill head while drilling, transportation uses such as train and automobile suspension systems; robotic operations in hazardous areas, and manufacturing elements which need high impact to precisely join or separate materials.

REFERENCES

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